

Designing and Evaluating User Experience in a Space through Emotion, Eye-Movements and Behavior

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Abstract

Evaluation of space design, like offices or stores, is not necessarily determined only by visual impressions. People's behavior is influenced by spaces, and equally, spaces are influenced by people's activities. In other words, a space does not exist as a fixed physical object; rather it is constructed by the interaction between people and spaces. Therefore, in space design, it is important to design not only a physical space, but also people's experiences. From such a viewpoint, we discuss the following framework for analyzing and evaluating space design, focused on the relationship between feelings, eye movements, and behavior.

1) Perform a Kansei-evaluation before and after experiencing a space to understand how experience affects emotions, 2) Record and analyze user behavior and eye movements to understand how people interact with a space, 3) Conduct retrospective interviews to understand the meaning and feeling of an experience.

We applied this framework to a bank, which was newly designed. From this case study, we were able to understand how users interacted with artifacts and information embedded in the space, and we obtained findings about the relation between user experiences and emotions. These findings provided implications for redesigning the space of the branch of a bank and confirmed the effectiveness of our framework.

Keywords: space design, user experience, Kansei-evaluation, eye movement analysis, behavior analysis, interaction, bank, case study

Introduction

With the spread of the Internet, various activities are becoming possible in this virtual space. Purchasing merchandise is a typical activity. People have begun to purchase many goods by mail order or through Internet auctions. With such a change in the retailing situation, the outlook toward physical space requires an alteration.

In addition, in the field of space design, the concept of designing buildings and spaces has also changed due to the influence of the situation theory. Designing a building or a space does not only involve the designing of a physical object or a visual object, but also designing the relationship between people and a building or a space. Based on this idea, the manner in

which a building or a space is evaluated must also change. Evaluating only the visual impression is not enough; instead it is important to evaluate the experience that a customer or a resident will have (Battarbee, 2003)(Heximer, 2002).

For example, the new PRADA store in New York was built based on the idea of what type of a “shopping experience” the store could provide for its customers (Koolhaas, 2001). In addition to a unique visual experience designed by Koolhaas, a customer can experience the surprise of using a digital fitting room, which provides a 360° panoramic view.

In such a trend, a new evaluation framework of space, based on the concept of user experience is also needed. Generally, in the evaluation of a store, a flow diagram is prepared and an eye tracking analysis of customers is conducted in order to evaluate and design the optimal mode of displaying goods. However, from the viewpoint of evaluating a customer’s experience, such evaluation methodology is not suitable. A new trend of evaluation was started by Underhill (Underhill, 2000, 2004) by conducting ethnographical research and analyzing detailed activities of customers from the viewpoint of shopping science. We can consider such activity as an example of user experience evaluation.

Our research focused on designing and evaluating the users’ experience in a space. We applied our methodology to a new branch of a bank, which had been constructed based on the new design concept. In this paper, we describe our evaluation framework, introduce a case study of the bank, and then report the findings and their implications.

A framework for analyzing and evaluating user experience in a space

An overview of our evaluation framework of user experience (i.e., a customer’s experience) in a space such as a store is shown in Figure 1. We assumed the following models.

- 1) With certain expectations, a customer selects a store and enters it.
- 2) Before entering the store, he looks around the space itself and interacts with visual materials (first impression).
- 3) Entering the store, he performs tasks to achieve his purpose. While performing tasks, he

interacts with various elements in the store. Such interactions form his new experience in the space. The elements include not only facilities but also information, people, and equipment. His feelings concerning that store are formed through these experiences.

Figure 1, A framework of analyzing and evaluating user experience

In our framework, we use the following analysis and evaluation methods.

1) Kansei Evaluation

In order to analyze and evaluate the emotional aspect of a customer, two kinds of evaluation methods are used.

a) Image Analysis (Database Image Survey)

From 180 image words, a subject chooses some words which he feels are appropriate to the evaluation target. The result of the analysis is represented as the color image map shown in Figure 2 (Kobayashi, 1992).

b) Subjective Evaluation (Semantic Differential Method: SD method)

A questionnaire including 17 questions regarding impression factors, eight questions regarding functional factors, and two questions regarding comprehensive factors is provided. A subject evaluates each criterion by ranking on a scale of seven.

Figure 2, An example of Color Image Map by Database Image Survey

2) Eye Movement and Behavioral Analysis

We instruct a subject to perform tasks which are normal in a store. While the subject is performing the tasks, his behavior and eye movements are recorded on videotapes. An interview is conducted after the tasks are completed. We investigate the causes and reasons for the subject's activities and his feelings at the time. The result of Eye Movement and Behavioral Analysis is visualized as a chart shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3, An example of Eye-Movement & Behavior Flow Map

Case study

In order to inspect the validity of our framework, we applied this framework to a new branch of a bank. This chapter discusses the case study.

Background

In the banking industry, because of the increase in ATM installations in convenience stores and widespread use of Internet banking, customers hardly ever visit the branches of banks. Even if they do visit the bank, they only use the ATM and do not enter the building. In response to this situation, each bank has increased the number of ATM-only branches, or has strategically improved Internet banking facilities. However, a major issue is the utilization of the banks' existing physical premises.

In addition to this trend, there exists a serious management issue in Japanese banks. It is that of changing from conventional company customers to individual customers, which is called "retailing." The issue, in other words, is how to build and reinforce the relationship between individual customers and a bank. In order to realize this purpose, it is important to break away from a uniform image, and promote the banks' merits and values to individual

customers. In response to this background, banks have started renovating their branches based on a new concept design.

A New Design Concept for a Bank

A certain bank has built a test branch based on a new design concept. We evaluate what sort of experience the customers gain from this branch and how they feel. An image of a conventional branch of a Japanese bank is shown in Figure 4. The bank clerks' working space and the customer floor is separated by a counter. Long chairs are arranged on the floor parallel to the counter, and the customers and bank clerks sit facing each other. The customer awaits his turn, sitting on a sofa for a while, and tasks are handled in a businesslike manner.

Figure 4, An typical Japanese bank layout and test branch's layout

The test branch partially follows this old Japanese style. However, the concept of welcoming individual customers is reflected in the design of the test branch. In particular, in order to entertain individual customers, the space has changed from that offering merely processing services to one offering other additional services. The space providing effective processing and the space providing comfortable seating are separated, and have been designed to convey different images. Even in the processing area, schemes conveying hospitality are embedded, for example a curved sofa arrangement aims to avoid a feeling of confrontation between bank

clerks and customers, so that the customers might feel more comfortable, even in the processing area.

Expected user experience

We assume the following scenario as an example of the user experience in the test branch.

1) Conventionally, a customer would visit a bank with an expectation of a sense of safety, reliability, and quick and correct processing. Today, a customer requires a bank where she can freely consult about individual assets.

2) For consultation regarding an intended investment, a customer comes to a bank. Usually, she searches for information on the Internet. However, she cannot decide which product is suitable for her, because the information available is not sufficient to make a judgment. She feels she needs thorough advice from a bank.

3) When she comes into the bank branch, she awaits her turn in a comfortable chair, looking at a catalog of investment information. She awaits her consultation in a calm and relaxing atmosphere.

4) When her turn comes, she goes to a consulting booth. The booth is surrounded by a translucent enclosure, providing sufficient privacy and a sense of security. From the careful explanation and useful advice of a bank clerk, she can fully understand her potential investment. Moreover, she can get information about new financial products, which are suitable for her. She goes home satisfied and will consider the investment product thoroughly.

Experiment

Simulation Environment

Since the test branch is not actually in business, there is no bank clerk and no customers, and the ATMs do not work. This is an unusual situation. In order to evaluate the user experience, it is necessary to reproduce real working conditions. About ten bank clerks participated in our experiment, and they played the roles of bank clerks and other customers. Furthermore, to increase the reality of the situation, real bank sounds were played, such as machine sounds,

number call sounds, ATM working sounds, etc.

Experimental equipments

For eye movement analysis, a subject carried out tasks equipped with an eye camera. In this experiment, we used the goggle-type eye camera, which has a head camera and eye-movement measurement unit (Figure 5). We analyzed the view images overlaid with eye movement tracking.

Figure 5, Eye Camera and a sample image of subject's view

Subjects

Group 1: Eye Movement and Behavioral Analysis + Kansei Evaluation: **6 subjects**

Group 2: Kansei Evaluation only: **15 subjects**

We chose subjects evenly on the basis of sex, age, and their bank. However, by an accident, the sex ratio became unbalanced (5 females vs. 1 male).

Tasks

We instructed the subjects to carry out tasks, which they usually perform in a real bank. Three subjects were instructed to perform an ATM task and a High-Counter task. Three more subjects were instructed to perform an ATM task and a Low-Counter task. The tasks assigned were as follows:

ATM task: Draw 30,000 yen from your bank account using an ATM.

High-Counter task: Transfer money to the directed bank account at a high counter.

Low-Counter task: Assume that you are considering managing assets of one million yen. Consult a bank clerk and find a financial product that is suitable for you.

Procedures

Step 1: Understand Expectations, Image Analysis)

Before looking at the bank, the subjects filled out a questionnaire. From 180 image words they chose less than 20 words, which they felt were appropriate to an ideal bank. (Database Image Survey)

Step 2: Evaluate First Impression (Image Analysis)

A subject entered the bank and quickly glanced around the interior. First impressions of the bank were then investigated using a questionnaire about image words and subjective criteria (Database Image Survey, SD method).

Step 3: Simulate the User Experience (Perform tasks in the test branch)

Step 3-1: Analyze interactions in the branch (Eye Movement and Behavioral Analysis)

A subject performed the instructed tasks. While performing, his activities were recorded from two viewpoints. One was a personal view, i.e., the viewpoint of the subject, and was recorded by the eye camera and the head camera. The other was a system view which was the observer's viewpoint and was recorded by a DV camera (Figure 6).

Figure 6, A sample image of personal view and system view

Step 3-2: Evaluate the Experience (Retrospective Interview)

After the subjects completed the tasks, we conducted retrospective interviews, reproducing the personal view by videotape, and asked them about the significance of the eye movements,

what they had seen, and how they had felt at the time. Reproducing the personal view helped in remembering the situation of the experience as accurately as possible.

Step 4: Evaluate the Emotional Aspect after the Experience (Image Analysis)

After subjects had completed all their assigned tasks, we investigated their feelings concerning the test branch with questionnaires, as in Step 2.

The steps assigned to each subject are shown in Table 1. Group 1 required approximately two hours, Group 2 required approximately one hour (per person).

		Group1	Group2
Step1	Understand the Expectation (Kansei Evaluation: Image Analysis)	●	●
Step2	Evaluate the First Impression (Kansei Evaluation: Image Analysis & SD Methods)	●	●
Step3	Simulate the User Experience (Perform tasks in the examination store)	●	
Step3-2	Analyze the Interactions in the space (Eye-movement & Behavioral Analysis)	●	
Step3-2	Evaluate the Experience (Retrospective Interview)	●	
Step4	Evaluate the Emotional aspect after the Experience (Kansei Evaluation: Image Analysis & SD Methods)	●	●

Group1: Eye-Movement & Behavioral Analysis + Kansei Evaluation (6 Subjects)
 Group2: Kansei Evaluation Only (15 Subjects)

Table 1, Procedural steps and task assignment

Results and implications

Were expectations satisfied? (Image of an Ideal Branch vs. First Impression)

The result of image analysis is shown in Figure 7. By comparing the ideal image with the image of the test branch, we were able to discover many common images. The common words were as follows: “intelligent” as representing feelings of functionality and reliability, “friendly” as representing a sense of affinity, “refreshing,” and “open” as representing a sense of beauty. From this result, we can say that the test branch mostly satisfied the requirements for the ideal image.

Words such as “familiar,” “comfortable,” and “pleasant,” which were included in the ideal branch image, were not expressed in the test branch image. As the concept of the test branch was to provide a comfortable space for customers, the lack of these images is a serious

problem. On the other hand, “sophisticated,” “stylish,” “modern,” “chic,” and “delicate” were extracted as images peculiar to the test branch. Although these differ from the customers’ sense of value for a bank, it is considered that these images could work well to add value to the test branch.

Figure 7, A result of Image Analysis (Ideal bank image vs. test branch image)

Changes in emotion before and after the experience

Figure 8 shows differences in feelings before and after the experience in the test branch. Although changes were not significant, the various image words that subjects selected had changed. In the first impression of the test branch, subjects had images such as “refreshing,” “intelligent,” “delicate,” “simple,” “artificial,” “smart,” “trim,” “sharp,” “modern,” and “calm.” This means they felt the test branch was polished and good-looking, but something inorganic. They felt it was not a human-oriented space. On the other hand, after performing the tasks, the image of the test branch changed. Subjects selected image words such as “friendly,” “tender,” “delicate,” “cheerful,” and “balmy.” These words represent a sense of affinity. In addition, they also selected “honest,” and “intellectual” which represent a feeling of trust.

This data is based on only 6 subjects in group1, who performed tasks.

Figure 8, A result of Image Analysis (Before vs. After Experience)

The SD analysis supports this result (Figure 9). The functional criteria hardly changed but the emotional criteria did change, and the score for most emotional criteria improved.

From these results, we could say that a new emotion was constructed through the experience in the test branch. In particular, the cold image was transformed to a warm image, providing a feeling of humanity. Why and how were these changes produced? We clarified this in the following section through interaction analysis.

Figure 9, A result of Subjective Evaluation (Before vs. After Experience)

Interaction Analysis

1) Behavior, eye movements, and information

For the ATM task, as soon as subjects entered a bank branch, they looked around for the ATMs and asked themselves questions such as “where is the tail end of the queue?” “how long is the line?” and “how many ATMs are occupied?” In this situation, their concern was “How long am I going to wait?” They rushed to the tail end of the queue, so their eye-gaze was focused on the ATM and its surroundings. Figure 10a shows the eye movement of a subject who was awaiting his turn in the queue. They hardly looked at the information.

After grasping the situation, the subject’s eyes absorb other information. From the result of eye movement analysis, the poster had the highest frequency of reference among the materials in the test branch. In addition, the duration of eye-gaze was longer than for any other objects. However, the subjects hardly understood the contents of the poster. For example, the poster in Figure 10a shows the number “0.5” written in a large font. Subjects were interested in that number, but to understand the meaning of the number, they needed to read an explanation written in a very small font. It was too small to read from their position in the queue, so it was impossible to understand the meaning of that poster. In the results, this poster played the role of an eye-catcher, but hardly provided any information to the subjects..

Figure 10, Interactions with various objects

2) The key factor responsible for emotional changes during the transition from a cold to a warm impression

In a retrospective interview, subjects said, “I felt a sense of reliability and energy when I saw the clerk’s activities,” “It was pleasant that bank clerks behaved in a crisp manner.” From such comments, it was found that subjects had good impressions of the bank clerks and their behavior. Subjects often shifted their gaze to the clerks (Figure 10b).

From the Kansei evaluation, we can discover emotional changes from a cold to a warm impression. Of course, various factors affected these changes in a complex fashion. However, the interaction between the subjects and bank clerks is considered as the key factor. In this experiment, some clerks were teachers who instructed bank clerks on how to act and entertain customers. Their model reception attitude is considered to have had a large influence on the subjects’ emotional evaluation. From this result, it is clear that people and their activities have a great effect on constructing impressions about a space. We confirmed this fact through our evaluation framework quantitatively and qualitatively.

3) Organizing the “waiting period”

There are many “waiting periods” in the activities of a branch of a bank. We observed that customers tend to shift their gaze toward various objects in a branch while waiting. Subjects feel that the waiting period is not desirable; hence, they try any means to make their waiting time meaningful. Therefore, they interact with various materials actively in order to make their waiting time valuable. For example, they look at posters on the wall or read magazines, and watch the bank clerk’s activities (Figure 10c).

Thus, subjects engaged in activities to obtain information actively. In the test branch, many general magazines were placed at random positions but in our post interview, subjects said, “I want to read financial articles or bank news.” If a bank can utilize the waiting period by providing valuable information more effectively, it will succeed in providing customers with a good user experience. However, in this test branch, the information provided was not sufficient to meet the user’s expectation of utilizing the waiting period more efficiently.

Issues of our Framework

As described above, from the result obtained by applying our framework to the new branch of a bank, we confirmed that this framework is useful and effective in analyzing and evaluating the user experience in the design of a new branch. On the other hand, some issues regarding our framework were raised.

1) Difficulty of application in the early design stage

Our framework requires subjects to perform tasks in a real space, which is essential to our evaluation. Therefore, the evaluation is often conducted at a late stage of the design process. Of course, our method is useful for evaluating an existing branch in order to design a new one, but it is hard to construct a real space in the early stages. It is next to impossible that the results and findings of the evaluation is reflected in a new design. We need an invention to strengthen our methodology for use in the evaluation of the early design phase.

2) Control the level of reality

As mentioned above, the “people” factor is very important in the user experience. In this experiment, with the cooperation of the bank, the simulation of the bank’s clerical process could be carried out with a high degree of authenticity. However, in an actual branch, there are many customers and not just one subject. Their movements and sounds are also highly important elements in constructing the environment and the atmosphere of a branch. We could not have a totally realistic situation because of the limitation on the number of people posing as customers. Controlling the level of reality in a test space, especially under restricted conditions, is another issue.

3) Improvement in equipment

In the experiment, subjects wore a goggle-type eye camera linked to a PC with a wired cable. Therefore, there was always an experimenter on the scene following the subject, and managing the wired cable so that the cord would not disturb the subject’s motions. This looked very strange to other customers. This affected the feelings and behavior of other customers, and it might have affected the subject’s evaluation result adversely. In order to evaluate the user experience at an existing branch, we need improvements in the eye camera and other equipment, to remove the sense of incongruity with the environment.

Conclusion

With a diversification in the selling channels, stores are changing from being places meant for selling to places meant for providing new experiences. Hence, conventional methods such as the flow diagram analysis are not sufficient to evaluate the user experience.

In designing a store, it is essential to evaluate and design the user experience. For this purpose, we propose a new methodology by integrating Kansei evaluation with eye movement and behavioral analysis. We applied our framework to a branch of a bank which was newly designed and built for testing. From this experiment, we confirmed the effectiveness of our framework and discovered many issues and their implications for redesign.

Though we propose a framework for evaluating user experience in a physical space such as a store, it is important to evaluate not only the physical store but also many other selling channels. Each requires its own methodology of evaluation depending on the channel's characteristics. Moreover, it is important to provide a total experience by integrating multiple channels, so we will try to develop a new methodology to evaluate an integrated experience using multiple channels.

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